

Physicochemical Investigations on the Complexation of Heavy Metal Ions with Dithiolterephthalic Acid. Part II Amperometric Study on the Complexes of Cu(II), Ag(I) & Pb(II)

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Manuscript received 22 August 1972; revised 12 January 1973; accepted 5 February 1973

The reactions between disodium dithiolterephthalate (L) and heavy metal ions viz., Cu^{2+} , Ag^+ and Pb^{2+} have been investigated amperometrically in the presence of 0.25 M KNO_3 and 0.001% Triton X-100 at $E_{d.e.} = -0.01$ volts vs. S.C.E. The breaks in titration curves reveal the formation of sparingly soluble complexes of composition (M:L) 1:1 in case of Cu(II) and Pb(II) and 2:1 in case of Ag(I).

In an earlier communication¹ the conductometric and potentiometric studies on the interaction of disodium dithiolterephthalate [referred to herein as $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$] with various ions were reported. Amperometric studies on the interaction of dithiolterephthalate with Cu(II), Ag(I) and Pb(II) amperometrically are reported below.

Experimental

Current measurements were made using a Cambridge (general purpose) polarograph coupled with a dropping mercury electrode and a saturated calomel electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics: $m = 1.427$ mg/sec, $t = 3.62$ sec. at zero volt (vs. S.C.E.) in 0.1M KNO_3 . Deaeration and stirring of solutions were carried out by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen. All titrations were carried out at 30°, maintained by an electrically operated thermostat.

Dithiolterephthalic acid was obtained from Evan's Chemetics, New York, (N.Y.). All other chemicals used were of Anala R. (B.D.H.) grade. Dithiolterephthalic acid is insoluble in water. A 0.1M stock solution of its disodium salt was prepared by digesting (3-4 days) a known weight of dithiolterephthalic acid with requisite amount of NaOH solution.

Results and Discussions

It has already been reported² that $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ depolarizes the mercury with the formation of an intermediate soluble mercurous compound which rapidly changes into an insoluble mercuric complex. The anodic wave corresponds to the two electron oxidation process and was found to be diffusion controlled, whose height depends on the concentration of the depolarizer. The proportionality of the diffusion current with concentration and the limiting current plateau potential, -0.01 volts vs. S.C.E. at which most of the heavy metal ions do not reduce, provide favourable conditions for performing amperometric titrations of metal ions.

In order to study the reactions of Cu(II), Ag(I) and Pb(II) and $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ a series of amperometric titrations were carried out using different concentrations of the reactants both by direct and reverse methods at $E_{d.e.} = -0.01$ volts and in the presence of 0.25M KNO_3 and 0.001% tirton X-100. Aliquots of titrant were added by means of a microburette and the observed currents after correction for dilution effect were plotted against volume of the titrant and the end points were located graphically. The results are summarised in table 1.

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC TITRATIONS BETWEEN Na_2 -DITHIOLTEREPHTHALATE AND Cu(II), Ag(I) AND Pb(II)

Metal ion	Equivalence point (ml)		Reacting ratio Metal-Ligand	Colour of the complex observed during titration
	Direct	Reserve		
Cu^{2+}	1.23	1.26	1 : 1	Red
	0.77	0.81		
Ag^{1+}	2.34	0.57	2 : 1	Dark brown
	1.60	0.42		
Pb^{2+}	1.18	1.27	1 : 1	Light yellow
	0.81	0.78		

Interaction with Cu(II) and Pb(II): Fig. 1 depicts the direct amperometric titrations between $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ and Cu(II), Ag(I), and Pb(II). When increasing amounts of Pb^{2+} ions were added (curve II) to $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ the anodic current given by $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ due to the anodic oxidation of $-\text{SNa}$ group, decreases linearly till the end point is reached, after which it becomes constant showing the completion of the

reaction. In case of Cu^{2+} (Curve-I) the anodic current decreases gradually assuming zero value at the end point. With the further addition the current increases again due to the reduction of the uncombined Cu^{2+} ions ($E_{\frac{1}{2}} = +0.02$ v vs. S.C.E.)³⁻⁵

Fig. 1. Direct amperometric titrations
 Curve I M/500 Ligand vs. M/30 CuSO_4
 Curve II M/500 Ligand vs. M/30 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.
 Curve III M/500 Ligand vs. M/30 AgNO_3 .

resulting in a straight line plot intersecting at galvanometer zero line. $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ reacts with both the metal ions forming 1 : 1 complexes.

In case of reverse titrations (Fig. 2) the current almost remains constant with the addition of $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ in case of Pb^{2+} (curve II) but in case of Cu^{2+} (curve I) the cathodic current produced by Cu^{2+} decreases gradually and linearly till the end point is reached after which in both the cases the anodic current produced by $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$ appears, which increases linearly with its further addition. Reverse titration curves also indicate the formation of 1 : 1 compound and substantiate the results obtained from direct amperometric titrations. The appearance of straight line plots in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ may be ascribed to the almost similar values of diffusion coefficients of Cu^{2+} ions and $\text{R}(\text{SNa})_2$. The result of amperometric titrations and infrared spectra of the Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} complexes⁶ show the formation of 1 : 1 linear polymer and coordination through the sulphur atom of the sulphhydryl group.

Interaction with $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$: The shape of the amperometric titration curves of Ag^+ (Fig. 1 and 2, Curve III) is almost similar to those obtained for $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, which is due to the reduction of $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ ions at potential at which titrations had been carried out. (The standard potential of the $\text{Ag}^+ - \text{Ag}$ couple is $+0.7995$ v. vs. N.H.E. Consequently the reduction of Ag^+ from non-complex-forming electrolytes produces diffusion current starting from zero applied e.m.f.)^{7,8}. In both direct and reverse titrations the end points were obtained from the point of interaction with the galvanometer zero line which corresponds to the molecular ratio, $\text{Ag}(\text{I}) : \text{R}(\text{SNa})_2 :: 2 : 1$. In this case the

formation of the following compound of given tentative structure, is observed.

Fig. 2. Reverse amperometric titrations.
 Curve I M/500 CuSO_4 vs. M/30 Ligand.
 Curve II M/500 $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ vs. M/30 Ligand.
 Curve III M/500 AgNO_3 vs. M/30 Ligand.

2:1 COMPLEX

The curved plots in case of direct titrations may be due to the solubility of the $\text{Ag}(\text{I})$ complex, in presence of the excess dithiolterephthalate.

In all the cases first addition of the reagent causes appreciable precipitation. Current values do not require much time for attaining steady state thus showing rapid interaction. The accuracy and the reproducibility of the results permit the adaptation of these reactions for the quantitative determination of the metal ions studied.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their thanks to Professor Dr. R. S. Saxena and Prof. R. M. Advani, Principal for providing research facilities. We are also indebted to the Ministry of Education, Government of India for awarding scholarship to one of us (A.V.P.) and to M/s Evan's Chemetics Inc., New York for a gift of dithiolterephthalic acid.

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